

Implementation of Presidential Regulation Number 12 of 2021 Concerning Government Procurement of Goods and Services in the City of Banjarmasin

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ABSTRACT

The title of this research is which aims to determine the description, supporting, and inhibiting factors as well as providing solutions faced in the Implementation of Presidential Regulation Number 12 of 2021 concerning the Procurement of Government Goods and Services in the City of Banjarmasin. His study uses qualitative research. The selection of information is carried out by purposive sampling, where researchers prefer to choose informants who meet certain criteria and are considered to know about what researchers expect and can be trusted with the accuracy of the information and know the problems in depth at the time of the interview. The results of this study indicate that the communication factors, resources, disposition, and approach to the implementation of Government Policy Number 12 of 2021 concerning Banjarmasin Goods and Services have not been realised optimally so that Presidential Regulation Number 12 of 2021 Procurement of goods and services has not run optimally. Factors in implementing the policy of Presidential Regulation Number 12 of 2021, namely the existence of Regional Regulations or other forms of regulations that exist at the local level as well as support for facilities and infrastructure including the availability of an operational budget determined through the APBD. On the external side, the DPRD's attention to efforts to implement the Presidential Regulation Number 12 of 2021 is very low.

INTRODUCTION

Procurement of Government Goods/Services is an activity to obtain goods and services by Ministries, Agencies, Regional Work Units, and other Institutions whose process starts from planning needs until the completion of all activities to obtain goods and services.

The process of procuring goods and services involves several related parties so ethics, norms, and principles for the procurement of goods and services are needed to be able to regulate or serve as the basis for determining policies for the procurement of goods and services. A good goods and services procurement system is a goods and services procurement system that is able to apply the principles of good governance, encourage efficiency and effectiveness in public spending, as well as structure the behavior of the three pillars are no longer foreign or new in the state and institutional arrangements in Indonesia. It also includes a management system for government procurement of goods based on the knowledge and experience routinely held by groups of bureaucrats over the past few years, which should be very conducive and accommodative towards the adoption of the four basic principles of governance as mentioned above. But as has become a habit in society.

The current problem is that various forms of procurement of government goods and services are carried out by many government agencies at the central and regional levels, where on the one hand the packaging meets all statutory and regulatory requirements criteria. However, if observed carefully and thoroughly, in reality, there are many deviations that are detrimental to state finances and the interests of the community.

The fact is in field based on the results of the author's observations indicate that procurement of government goods/services in the City Government of Banjarmasin seems dominated by certain parties or people who are indicated to be close to the interests. Therefore, without realizing it, the community, as the largest and most important beneficiary in the implemented development system of the government, turns out that in reality receiving the end result of the process of procuring goods and services that are not appropriate terms of quality, quantity, benefits, objectives, delivery time, and price than they should be. Procurement of goods/services carried out by the government is intended to obtain goods/services at exact criteria price, the right (according) quality, the right quantity (volume), the right partner and method of procurement, and other agreements in accordance with the agreement made so that users can utilize the goods/services promote sustainable procurement.

As an example of a case that occurred, the criminal act of corruption in a development project resulted in the degradation of the quality of the results of the procurement of goods and services, as well as hindering the government's efforts to recover the national economy. So that the community as beneficiaries becomes the most disadvantaged party. The Corruption Eradication Commission has named AW as Hulu Sungai Utara Regent for the period 2017 to 2022 as a suspect for alleged corruption in the form of accepting gifts or promises by state administrators or those representing them related to the

procurement of goods and services in Hulu Sungai Utara Regency, South Kalimantan in 2021-2022. This case began with the KPK's red-handed activities on September 15, 2021. In this activity, the KPK has named several parties as suspects, namely the MK as Plt. Kadis PU at DinasPUPRT North Hulu Sungai Regency as well as PPK and KPA, MRH as the Director of CVHanamas, and FH as the Director of CV Kalpataru. A regional head as a state administrator who is paid from the people's money should be a good role model in creating clean, transparent, and accountable governance in his territory. Instead of denying the mandate of his position to gain personal and group benefits through corrupt practices. (Banjarmasin.tribune.com 2021)

With the principles of efficient, effective, transparent, open, competitive, fair or non-discriminatory, and accountable procurement for all parties, the results will be properly accounted for. The principles mentioned above will become the legal basis for procuring actors (providers and users), and if they do not follow the principles and regulations will face law enforcement. This rule article discusses the Policy Implementation of Presidential Regulation Number 12 Years 2021 About Procurement of Goods/ Government Services.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Public Policy Concept

Public Policy according to (Thomas R. Dye, 1995:2) is "what government to do, what they do it and what difference it makes". Everything that the government does, why they do it, and the results that make a life together look different.

Meanwhile, according to Lasswell and Kaplan (1970:71), Public Policy is defined as "a project program of goals, values, and practices" namely as something projected program with a specific purpose certain values, and practices certain practices.

Many experts define Public Policy, these definitions are all correct and complementary. While some scientist in Indonesian uses the term Wisdom instead of policy, wisdom is not policy, because (wisdom) is one of the characteristics of an excellent public policy.

Policy Implementation

Policy implementation is a very important aspect of the entire policy process because public policies that have been made will be beneficial when implemented. A policy program must be implemented in order to have the desired impact or goal. Implementation is seen as a process of interaction between a set of goals and actions capable of achieving policy goals. Where inside the implementation of policies actors, organizations, procedures and techniques are used together and simultaneously. This definition means that implementing something must be accompanied by supporting facilities which will later impact the consequences of something (Wahab, 1997: 67).

Van Meter and Van Horn in Wahab (1997: 65), stated that: The implementation process is the actions carried out by individuals or offices or groups-government or private groups directed at achieving the goals outlined in the policy decision). Policy implementation is an effort to achieve certain

goals by means- certain means and in a certain time sequence (Bambang Sunggono 1994: 137).

Government Goods/Services Procurement Policy

In the implementation of procurement, the user is a party that requests or gives assignments to the provider to supply or manufacture goods or carry out certain work. Users of goods and services can be an institution/organization and can also be individuals. which are classified as institutions including Government agencies (Central Government, Provincial Government, Regency Government, City Government), Business Entities (BUMN, BUMD, Private), and community organizations.

METHODOLOGY

This research was conducted in natural conditions. Sugiyono (2013) suggests that qualitative research methods are research methods used to examine natural object conditions, where researchers are key instruments, data collection techniques are carried out in triangulation (combined), data analysis is inductive, and qualitative research results emphasize meaning rather than generalization.

object naturally referred to by Sugiyono (2013) object which is what it is, not manipulated by the researcher so that the conditions when the researcher enters the object, after being in the object and after leaving the object relatively unchanged. So while conducting research regarding the implementation of the presidential regulation policy number 12 of 2021 concerning Procurement of Goods/Services in the city of Banjarmasin, the researchers did not regulate the conditions in which the research took place or manipulated variables.

The main characteristics that are of concern in qualitative research are meaning. In this case, naturalistic research does not care about the similarities of object research but vice versa-reveal about different views on life. This thinking is also based on the fact that the meaning of each person is different.

Based on Frankl's theory (1969) which states that there is no general or the same meaning in life between humans but unique meanings that come from individual situations, when researchers conduct research on Policy Implementation of Presidential Regulation Number 12 of 2021 concerning Procurement of Goods/Services in Banjarmasin City, it is necessary to use a phenomenological approach. This is in accordance with what was stated by Moleong (2007), namely that researchers in a phenomenological view try to understand the meaning of events and their relationships to people who are in certain situations. So by using a phenomenological approach, researchers are trying to explore the values of experience in the procurement of goods/services.

Source information that will be used in this research includes 3 (three) SKPD in an environment of Banjarmasin City Government, namely, the first Section Procurement Goods/Services of the Regional Secretariat Banjarmasin City. The second is the Department of Public and Spatial Planning of Banjarmasin City. The third is the Department of Housing and Regions Settlement Banjarmasin City.

RESEARCH RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Implementation Process procurement of goods and services based on Presidential Regulation Number 12 of 2021 at the Regional Secretariat of the City of Banjarmasin. The Regional Secretariat is an element of staffed by a Regional Secretary and is under and responsible to the Mayor. Those who have the duty and obligation to assist the Mayor in formulating policies in coordinating with regional offices and regional technical institutions. Problems in the procurement of goods and services can befall everyone, including regional apparatus organizations (OPD), in carrying out their duties, They are not free from mistakes it can be detrimental to society, they need agencies or other services that bridge to resolve a problem. The governing authority in this case includes regional authority to carry out national development in an effort to improve public services and develop the national and regional economy. In connection with the above, the Procurement of Goods and Services Section of the Regional Secretariat of the City of Banjarmasin is an element of staff and one of the regional apparatus organizations The regional secretariat has an important role in the implementation to realize the procurement of government goods and services asmentioned in on the need for arrangements that provide fulfillment of the maximum value of the benefits (*value for money*) and contribute to increasing the use of domestic products, increasing micro, small and medium enterprises and sustainable development.

Implementation of Presidential Regulation No. 12 Year Policy 2021 Regarding Procurement Government Goods and Services in the City of Banjarmasin in the theory of George C. Edward III are very important in measuring the implementation of public policy, namely:

Communication

Pointing Communication that every policy will be implemented properly if there is good effective communication between program implementers (policies) and the target group or (target group). communication is done vertically as well horizontal as well as socialization in the process of procuring goods and services, so as to support the successful implementation of regulatory policies.

Presidential Regulation Number Presidential Regulation Number 12 of 2021 in the Procurement of Government Goods and Services at the Regional Secretariat of the City of Banjarmasin. Since the enactment of the policy, there are still deficiencies in the implementation of the policy. The problems that have become obstacles to date are ineffective communication between

superiors and staff, as well as the lack of information received by implementers and other staff which of course has an impact on the implementation of the policy.

Communication indicates that any policy can be implemented properly if there is good effective communication between program implementers (policies) and the target group (*target group*). According to Edward III in Widodo (2001) in communication, there are three dimensions that affect policy including the transmission dimension (*transmission*), clarity (*clarity*), and consistency (*consistency*).

From the results of research associated with factor Implementation communication socialization of Presidential Regulation Number 12 of 2021 Concerning Procurement of Government Goods and Services in the City of Banjarmasin, namely by carrying out outreach to all SKPDs within the Banjarmasin City Government, coordination meetings and opening consultation services to SKPD/Stakeholder against PBJ. Socialization held regarding the Regulations President Number 12 of 2021 carries out these rules through consultation of each SKPD in providing understanding and explanation in detail to the SKPD within the Banjarmasin City Government, regarding the implementation of PBJ procurement. This shows that Presidential Regulation Number 12 of 2021 concerning Government Procurement of Goods/Services is clearly known.

Implementation Presidential Regulation Number 12 of 2021 Regarding Procurement of Goods and Services The Government emphasizes that the procurement of goods/services is one of the driving forces of the economy in which it provides the widest possible employment opportunities, makes it easier for the community, especially Small Micro Enterprises (UMK) to open new businesses and supports PBJ's corruption prevention and eradication efforts are ranked second after bribery. Within the rules of the Regulations President No. 12 of 2021, the government's alignment in supporting Micro, Small, and Cooperative Enterprises, as well as the use of domestic products is carried out by stipulating the obligation for Ministries/Institutions/Regional Governments (K/L/PD) to allocate at least 40 percent of the value of the goods expenditure budget /service.

The explanation above shows that communication so far has been good both vertically and internally as well as socialization and evaluation, so as to overcome all problems that arise in the process of procurement of government goods and services. So the communication factor is said to support the implementation Policy for Presidential Regulation Number 12 of 2021 concerning the procurement of government goods/services in the City of

Banjarmasin. However, it still needs to be held periodically, It can be said that every policy that has been set does not always work well, sometimes policies encounter problems in the implementation process, as described above.

As explained by Edward III in Tahir (2014: 62) Information about public policy needs to be communicated to policymakers so that policymakers know what they have to prepare and do to implement the policy so that the goals and objectives of the policy can be achieved as expected. Communication determines successful achievement of goals from implementation. Execution effectively happens when decision-makers already know what to do. Knowledge of what to do can work if communication goes well so that every decision and implementation regulation must be transmitted (communicated) to the right personnel department. The success of an implementation policy According to Hogwood and Gunn in Fauzan (2018), communication plays an important role in the ongoing coordination of policy implementation. According to Hogwood and Gunn quoted by Wahab coordination not only concerns the issue of communicating information or establishing appropriate administrative structures but also concerns other issues more basic, namely the practice of implementing policies.

If implementation is effective, then which responsible answer for implementing a decision should know what will be implemented. To implement The policy must be transmitted to the appropriate personnel, and this policy must be clear, accurate, and consistent.

Human Resources and Financial Resources

One of the most important sources in implementing policies is staff, but the number of staff does not always have an effect on implementing a policy. This means that a large number of staff does not automatically encourage optimal successful policy implementation, due to the lack of knowledge possessed by government employees or staff in each work unit. But on the other hand staff shortages will also raise complex issues regarding effective policy implementation. Public services in Indonesia are often said to be slow and tend to be inefficient. The reason lies in the lack of staff handling these public services, as well as the lack of quality resources and the low motivation of employees to work.

The existing human resource factor really needs participation to implement Presidential Regulation No. 12 of 2021 in the procurement of government goods/services in the CityBanjarmasin Total There are 20 HR people, both as staff, system administration, activity support implementers and LOKJA (Functional). Apart from being academically (S1) implementers are also equipped with Bimtek and obtain Competency Certification for

processes/sections/stages of PBJ implementation. not only that, implementing these regulations also requires funds to help implement them, especially in increasing human resources and upgrading/maintaining equipment (hardware, software, and internet network rental). The availability of funds provided for the implementation of Presidential Regulation No. 12 of 2021 regarding the procurement of government goods/services in the City of Banjarmasin is Rp. 1,593,000, - allocated for internet operations, Software and Hardware (Purchasing/maintenance), Bintek PBJ, and official travel (proof of field qualifications).

Construction by comprehensive always held for the creation of human resources professionals, by carrying out technical guidance related to the duties, principles, and functions of each, The budget allocated although limited, can be realized in sustainable coaching programs. Related to this factor, it shows that human resources and financial resources have supported the success of the Policy Implementation of Presidential Regulation Number 12 of 2021 Concerning Government Procurement of Goods/Services in the City of Banjarmasin.

In reality, the availability of facilities in each work unit is very diverse, and in general, they are available and their utilization has been carried out but not yet effective and optimal. In terms of the resource aspect, the availability of facilities shows that the existing facilities already support the implementation of Presidential Regulation Number 12 of 2021 in the Procurement of Government Goods and Services at the Regional Secretariat of the City of Banjarmasin.

Even though the contents of the policy have been communicated clearly and consistently, regarding Presidential Regulation Number 12 of 2021 in Procurement of Government Goods and Services at the Regional Secretariat of Banjarmasin City, a lack of implementers resources to carry out the implementation will not work effectively. Resources are an important factor for policy implementation to be effective. According to Edward III in Tahir (2014: 66) says that "factor resource has an important role in policy implementation. These resources include resource human resources, budgetary resources, equipment resources, and authority resources.

Construction by comprehensive always held for the creation of human resources professionals, by carrying out technical guidance related to the duties, principles, and functions of each, The budget allocated although limited, can be realized in sustainable coaching programs. Related to this factor, it shows that human resources and financial resources have supported the success of the Policy Implementation of Presidential Regulation Number 12

of 2021 Concerning Government Procurement of Goods/Services in the City of Banjarmasin.

There is technical guidance always held for creation the of human resources professionals and competent, carrying out technical guidance related to their respective duties, principles, and functions, but due to budget constraints allocated limited, this is a separate obstacle in realizing sustainable coaching programs and there are still many apparatus Those in charge of this Section are concurrently serving as procurement officials in the Regional Apparatus Organizational Environment (OPD) and some even handle up to 3 to 6 Agencies or Services.

Disposition

Disposition refers to characteristics that are closely attached to the implementer of a policy or program. The disposition or attitude of the implementer is the third factor in public policy implementation. Implementation is to continue with a disposition in the implementation of this public policy is defined as the tendency, desire, or agreement of the implementers (implementers) to implement the policy. Policy implementation, If you want to succeed effectively and efficiently, the implementers (implementers) not only have to know what to do and have the ability to carry out the policy, but they must also have the will to carry out the policy.

Implementers have great discretion in implementing policies. According to Edward in Wahab (2008) many policies enter the "zone of indifference". There are policies that are implemented effectively because they receive support from policy implementers, but other policies may be in direct conflict with the views of policy implementers or the organizational interests of implementers. Here it trend- the tendency to create obstacles - barriers to implementation.

Disposition refers to characteristics that are closely attached to the implementer of a policy or program. The characteristics possessed by the implementer are honesty, commitment, and democracy. Regarding the character of the executor/implementor of Presidential Regulation Number 12 of 2021 Concerning Procurement of Goods/Services in the city of Banjarmasin which includes the level of commitment and honesty.

From the results of the research, the Implementer is very knowledgeable in his field according to the level of PBJ experts in functions and duties, upholds honesty, is democratic, and is committed according to the facts of integrity as ASN. Mastering in the PBJ field, namely competency certification for procurement officials at the basic level or Level I, as well as following the

functional level of the First PBJ Expert in accordance with the functions and duties.

The response given by the implementor when superiors ask to implement the regulatory policy is "Positive". Also, the agreement made between superiors and staff before implementing the policy has the same statement, The results of the research show that before the policy is implemented an agreement is made between superiors and staff, any changes to PBJ rules must be implemented so that the aims and objectives of the policy to be implemented are known. In accordance with the mandate of Presidential Regulation Number 12 of 2021, it must be held by every policy in K/D/L/I so that the implementation of the policy complies with regulations. Regarding the knowledge of the implementor, this policy is very competent, because it already has competency certification, so it is very knowledgeable in its field according to the level of PBJ experts in functions and duties, as well as commitment integrity as ASN.

According to Edward III in Tahir (2014: 67) Disposition is "the character or characteristics or attitudes possessed by the implementor such as commitment, honesty, democratic nature". If the implementor has a good disposition, then he will run policies as well as what policymakers want. When the implementer has different characteristics or perspectives from the policymakers, the policy implementation process will also not be effective.

Based on the results of the interview above, it can be concluded that the disposition factor is very supportive of the successful implementation of Presidential Regulation Policy Number 12 of 2021 concerning the procurement of government goods/services in the City of Banjarmasin.

In the disposition of implementers to proceed effectively, not only must implementers know what must be done and have the capacity to do this, but they must also be willing to carry out a policy. Most implementers can make proper selections in policy implementation. The reason for this is its independence from the nominal superiors who formulate policies. Another reason is the complexity of their own policies.

Bureaucratic Structure

The bureaucratic structure becomes important in policy implementation where this aspect of bureaucratic structure includes two important things, the mechanism aspect, and the implementing organizational structure itself. If there are insufficient resources to implement a policy and implementers know what needs to be done and want to do it, implementation may still be prevented due to deficiencies in the bureaucratic structure. Organizational

Format may hinder necessary coordination for implementing successfully a complex policy that requires the cooperation of many people.

The bureaucratic structure is a very important element in implementing a policy. Policy implementers know what to do and have enough desire and resources to do it. But in practice still inhibited by organizational structures. Implementation of policies in an inefficient bureaucratic structure requires cooperation with a large number of personnel, there is no coordination due to organizational fragmentation which causes wasted resources for nothing, creates doubts, and inhibits change. The results of the study found that there are SOPs that can facilitate and uniform implementation of the policy. Making SOPs that are carried out according to the rules in accordance with the operational guidelines and technical guidelines for LKPP as an organization at the maturity level of UKPBJ Level I. However, the implementing bureaucracy still relies on the PBJ section.

The organizational structure will work well in implementing an activity if it is supported by work procedures, division of labor, and well-organized cooperation and coordination. Judging from the aspect of bureaucratic structure, policy implementation has not been able to run effectively. The results of the study found that work procedures were made in a unified guideline in understanding the procedures for procuring goods and services which indeed had to have a guidebook to standardize policy implementation and make it easier for implementers to implement President Number 12 of 2021 in the Procurement of Government Goods and Services at the Regional Secretariat of Banjarmasin City. The standard operating procedure (SOP) should be disseminated to all OPD or SKPD from one source and followed by another OPD or SKPD.

It can be concluded that one of the conditions that supports the implementation of policies effectively, is Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) for making work procedures. This aims to standardize the policies that will be implemented. The organizational structure is not only based on standard operating procedures but must also be supported by the available budget to carry out an activity.

Increasing institutional maturity implemented in accordance with Presidential Regulation Number 12 of 2021 received support from all central and regional parties by stipulating Standard operational procedure (SOP), so that in the Procurement of Goods/Services section the Regional Secretariat of Banjarmasin City becomes the center of excellence for UKPBJ or *Center of Excellence* (COE) throughout Indonesia with increasing variable values. Bureaucratic Structure indicates that bureaucratic structure is important in

implementation policy This aspect of bureaucratic structure includes two important things, first is the aspect of mechanism, and the organizational structure executor himself. in the Regional Regulation of the City of Banjarmasin Number 133 of 2019 regarding the formation and composition of the Regional Apparatus, then the Regional Government of the city of Banjarmasin issued the Regulation of the Mayor of Banjarmasin Number 81 of 2019 concerning Position, Organizational Structure, Duties and Functions and Work Procedures of the Regional Secretariat of the City of Banjarmasin which includes the Formation of Units Procurement work for goods and services for the Banjarmasin city government and regulations for the mayor of Banjarmasin Number 56 of 2021 concerning the Code of Ethics for the Procurement of Goods and Services for the Government of the City of Banjarmasin, from this regulation we can see an overview of the performance carried out by the Goods and Services Procurement Section of the Regional Secretariat of the City of Banjarmasin. The program implementation mechanism has usually been established through Standard Operating Procedures(SOP)listed in the program guidelines/policy.

According to Edward III in Tahir (2014: 150) "There are main characteristics of the bureaucracy namely: "*Standard Operating Procedure (SOP)* and fragmentation". According to Winarno (2014: 150). *Standard Operational Procedure (SOP)* is the development of internal demands for certainty of time resources and the need for uniformity in complex and broad work organizations. Edward III in Winarno (2014: 107) also emphasized that "It is clearly emphasized whether the standard of operation is good regarding mechanisms, systems, and procedures for implementing policies, the division of main tasks, functions and authorities, and responsibilities among actors, and disharmony relations between organization executors with each other as well determine successful policy implementation". In the view of Edward III in Tahir (2014: 152) explained "That SOP is very likely to be an obstacle to the implementation of new policies that need it new ways of working or types employee to implement policies. Thus, the more a policy requires a change in the usual ways within an organization, the greater probability SOP hinders implementation". Thus Edward III emphasized the importance of SOP in implementing a policy so that directed coordination can be created for the implementation of each responsibility in the bureaucratic structure.

This factor has greatly contributed to the successful implementation of Presidential Regulation No. 12 of the 2021 Policy concerning Procurement of Government Goods/Services in the City of Banjarmasin. Even though the resources for implementing a policy are sufficient, the implementers (implementers) know what and how to do it, and have the desire to do it.

Procurement of government goods and services has an important role in ensuring the success of regional apparatuses in carrying out strategic missions and development work programs. The implementation of the Procurement Center of Excellence or the center of excellence in procurement, in line with the institutional evolution proclaimed by LKPP, provides a framework that allows the Goods and Services Procurement Work Unit - UKPBJ to develop from a reactive unit with a compliance-oriented approach to a proactive customer-oriented service unit, to ensure strategic procurement activities within the government environment can be implemented so as to support the achievement of the organization's strategic vision and mission.

Strategy*Center of Excellence*

The institutional character of the Goods and Services Procurement Section in one of its roles as the Goods and Services Procurement Work Unit (UKPBJ) as *Center Of Excellence* (COE) strategically realizes the procurement function which plays a critical role in achieving organizational goals through planning and execution of budgets and effective management of resources. Collaboratively foster collaboration and synergy among stakeholders for optimal performance of the procurement function. In a work orientation to build a performance-based culture in the procurement function to increase added value in 4 areas (processing time, cost, quality, and procurement service level).

On the proactive side, creating a paradigm shift in the customer-oriented supply chain of goods and services. Continuously enhance the capabilities of procurement organizations as learning organizations by adopting procurement best practices.

Coaching and management center of excellence planning and implementation of procurement of goods/services as a center of excellence for Government Procurement of Goods/Services has three functions, namely the Guidance Function of Government procurement of goods and services including carrying out procurement strategies, facilitating technical guidance and/or training, Carrying out consultations and/or assistance, including providing recommendations, and carry out the facilitation of human resource development.

The function of implementing government procurement of goods/services carries out tasks which include carrying out the selection of goods/services providers through auctions, selection, direct appointment and/or direct procurement, carrying out the selection of goods/services providers through the government cooperation mechanism with business entities, carrying out the selection of goods/services providers whose funds are

sourced from foreign loans/grants, carry out the selection of goods/services providers to be included in the electronic catalog, from the pre-electronic catalog process to the post-electronic catalog process, in the context of implementing local electronic catalogs, planning and implementing government goods/services procurement contracts for K/L/D/I who do not have resource human beings who have the required competence, if requested by the K/L/D/I.

The function of managing the information system for government procurement of goods/services carries out tasks which include managing the entire information system for government procurement of goods/services, including SIRUP, SPSE, e-catalog, e-monev, SIKaP, and others, carrying out government goods/services procurement services electronically, guide the implementation of registration and carry out user verification of all information systems for government procurement of goods/services, carry out the development of information systems required by UKPBJ, and carry out the asset management information function.

a. Supervision

Procurement of government goods/services (PBJ), which is one of the activities carried out by the government in order to support the implementation of government duties and functions, and improve public services, so that government procurement of goods/services also determines the success of achieving government goals. Procurement of goods/services The government has adopted new things in the process of procuring goods/services including the development of e-marketplaces, more intensive use of information technology, communication, and electronic transactions, as well as encouraging the implementation of research and creative industries. On the other hand, it is emphasized that the procurement of goods/services must apply principles of efficient, effective, transparent, open, competitive, fair, and accountable. The role of the Government Internal Supervisory Apparatus (APIP) is clearly stated in Government Regulation Number 60 of 2008 concerning the Government Internal Monitoring System. According to Articles 47 and 48 of Government Regulation Number 60 of 2008, APIP must carry out internal supervision over the implementation of the duties and functions of Government Agencies including accountability for state finances. The Government of Indonesia's Internal Audit Standards (SAIPI) also state that APIP's role is to provide reasonable assurance of compliance, thrift, efficiency, and effectiveness in achieving the objectives of implementing the duties and functions of government agencies, providing early warning and increasing the effectiveness of risk management in carrying out the duties and functions of government agencies (anti-corruption activities), as well as providing input

that can maintain and improve the quality of governance in the implementation of duties and functions of government agencies, including in the process of procuring government goods/services. Article 76 of Presidential Regulation Number 16 of 2018 states that Ministers/heads of Institutions/heads of regions are required to supervise the procurement of goods/services through the internal control apparatus (APIP). APIP according to Presidential Regulation Number 16 of 2018, in article 1 point 22 states that APIP carries out supervision through audits, reviews, monitoring, evaluation, and other supervisory activities on the implementation of Government duties and functions. Supervision carried out by APIP is carried out from planning, preparation, selection of providers, execution of contracts, and handover of work. In order to enhance APIP's role in carrying out internal control over the procurement of goods/services, particularly to improve governance, control, risk management, and prevention of fraud, general guidelines for internal control over the procurement of goods/services and other technical guidelines are needed to help APIP effectively. supervise the procurement of goods/services through various types of appropriate supervision. APIP carries out supervision through audits, reviews, monitoring, evaluation, and other supervisory activities on the implementation of the Government's duties and functions. Supervision carried out by APIP is carried out from planning, preparation, selection of providers, execution of contracts, and handover of work. BPKP is an institution tasked with fostering the implementation of good governance (*good governance*), including in terms of the implementation of the internal control system in the process of procurement of goods/services, providing general guidelines for internal control over the procurement of goods/services for APIP and related technical guidelines.

There are three stages in the supervision activities carried out by APIP on goods/services procurement activities. First, the planning stage, which includes reviewing the Work Plan and Budget Ministry of State/Institution (RKAK/L). Then, a review of the State Property Requirements Plan (RKBMN). Particularly for the procurement of land and buildings as well as motorized vehicles, supervision has been carried out since the RKBMN stage which must be prepared by each work unit.

Next, review the Procurement Planning. For high-risk procurement activities, APIP provides assistance with procurement planning, including reviewing the preparation of Self-Estimated Prices (HPS) to gain confidence that the HPS prepared has been equipped with adequate supporting data and the Work Unit has carried out a risk analysis and risk control plan-procurement risk.

Second, the stage of procurement implementation. APIP will carry out supervision in the form of reviewing budget absorption and Procurement of Goods and Services periodically every quarter, the results of these activities are used internally and reported to the Agency Financial and Development Supervision (BPKP). For high-risk activities, APIP provides assistance or supervision regularly during the fiscal year or up to the completion of work. This is intended if there are irregularities/obstacles, APIP can immediately provide recommendations for improvement, in accordance with APIP's role as an early *warning system* so that it is hoped that audit findings related to these high-risk procurement activities can be minimized.

Third, the Post-Procurement or Accountability stage. In this stage, the supervision carried out by APIP is in the nature of quality assurance (assurance), with activities carried out in the form of audits to see the remaining risks of procurement of goods, as well as providing assistance during external inspections if necessary.

Regarding the implementation of procurement of goods and services at UKPBJ Banjarmasin, especially in 2022, the Banjarmasin City Inspectorate recommends several things, including accelerating self-management activities so that it will also accelerate budget realization, considering that for this year the Ministry of Industry targets budget absorption of up to 60 percent on end of semester I. Next, accelerate the procurement of goods and services and include it in the General Procurement Planning Information System (SIRUP) application. This is mainly for procurements that require a long time to complete, such as construction work, procurement of machines/equipment that are not ready stock, and the procurement of goods that must be imported from abroad. by maximizing procurement by e-purchasing, especially because the Banjarmasin City government already has a sectoral catalog, so it is hoped that the implementation of goods/services within the Ministry of Industry will be more effective, efficient, and accountable.

b. Control

Early procurement of goods and services will encourage better implementation of program activities, especially implementation of strategic infrastructure provision with a large budget and high complexity. In addition, being able to provide the widest possible space for planning and implementing activities, so that the spread of activity implementation can be distributed within one year, not concentrated at the end of the year.

c. Coordination

Implementation of a regulation needs support and coordination with other agencies. For this reason, coordination and cooperation between agencies

is needed for the success of a regulation. Preparation of PBJ for the 2021 Fiscal Year which involved the General/Equipment Section of the finance department for all Echelon I Units at the end of last July as an effort to equalize the perceptions of PBJ managers so that they can synergistically run all PBJ programs with all work units within the Ministry of Finance with good performance, high performance, and integrity.

The steps taken to able to implement the budgeting strategy include an integrated procurement process where coordination with all relevant stakeholders continues to be built. Then always strengthen the HR capacity of PBJ managers and implement a number of managerial *tools that* can help increase the effectiveness and efficiency of the PBJ process, among others *Supply Position Model* (SPM).

Supply Position Model is used as a tool in an effort to facilitate the mapping of PBJ packages in each category so that procurement priorities and appropriate handling can be determined proportional to limited resources. SPM is also used to mitigate PBJ risks according to the category, for example how procurement is included in the categories, *Bottleneck, Leverage, or Routin* then from the SPM profiling a strategy can be determined procurement as well as appropriate procurement implementation assistance strategies to achieve the best procurement performance that supports the achievement of the organizational performance of the Ministry of Finance.

So that with the implementation of This coordination is expected to provide benefits as well *insight* new opportunities for PBJ managers and each Echelon I Unit to further synergize the process of planning, budgeting, and implementing goods/services procurement.

d. Institutional Strengthening

In increasing the maturity of the goods/services procurement agency, the Bureau of Procurement of Goods/Services has endeavored to fulfill institutional improvement indicators and input supporting evidence into the application. SI UKPBJ so that in 2019 it can reach the institutional maturity level of goods/services procurement with the achievement of level 2 (essence level). This achievement was also reflected in the formation of UKPBJ which was previously under the General Bureau (Procurement Service Unit Section) and has now become the Bureau of Procurement of Goods/Services. In the future, the Goods/Services Procurement Bureau is expected to become a Center of Excellence that has character, is strategic, collaborative and performance-oriented, and proactive. Increasing the Maturity Level of Goods/Services Procurement Agencies is carried out through the following programs:

Apparatus Facilities and Infrastructure Improvement Program and Apparatus Resources Capacity Building Program.

e. Integrity

Integrity on procurement of goods and services, that is, will not carry out KKN practices. Will report to the authorities/authorities if they find out that there are indications of KKN in this auction process. In this procurement process, promise to carry out tasks in a clean, transparent, and professional manner in the sense that they will have optimal capabilities and resources to provide the best work results starting from the preparation of bids, implementation, and completion of this work/activity.

If I violate the things that I have stated in this Integrity Pact, the managers of the procurement of goods and services are willing to be subject to moral sanctions, administrative sanctions as well as compensation and criminal prosecution in accordance with the provisions of the applicable laws and regulations.

the integrity pact is still maintained in the presidential regulation. Setting an integrity pact in the procurement of government goods/services is one of the efforts to realize good and clean governance (*good governance and clean government*). However, what is more, important is the application of material from the pledge to prevent and not engage in collusion, corruption, and nepotism as stated in the integrity pact. The implementation of the integrity pact in the procurement of government goods/services is one of the government's efforts to realize good and clean governance (*good governance and clean government*)

The general objective of the CoE is to build the capabilities of government procurement organizations in planning, operational management, and monitoring of procurement to achieve procurement principles. With the application, Ino created a procurement organization that can carry out a strategic role to achieve organizational goals. Creating effective communication and cooperative relationships with all stakeholders in the supply chain, including building social networks. Implemented throughout the management performance of procurement of goods and services to ensure the achievement of organizational performance. Creation of an integrated procurement process to increase internal and external customer satisfaction. Creation of learning organizations in the function procurement to be able to create a center of excellence in sharing knowledge, information, and capabilities.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the discussion of research results and the discussion that has been presented, the conclusion taken as a whole as follows:

Implementation of Presidential Regulation Number 12 of 2021 Policy concerning Procurement of Government Goods/Services in the City of Banjarmasin has been running quite optimally, this is because there are all indicators that have been fulfilled in supporting the success of Policy Implementation Presidential Regulation Number 12 of 2021. communication factors, resources, disposition, and bureaucratic structure as an approach to Policy Implementation have been realized quite optimally.

Factors supporting the implementation of the Presidential Regulation No.12 Year 2021 namely the existence of Regional Regulations or other forms of regulations that exist at the local level as well as support for facilities and infrastructure including the availability of an operational budget determined through the APBD. On the external side, the DPRD's attention to the implementation of Presidential Regulation No. Year 2021 Very high. The inhibiting factor is that there are still those who do not know and understand the implementation of this policy so it will become a problem in the future if this is not handled immediately.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

This research still has limitations so it is necessary to carry out further research related to the topic "Implementation of Presidential Regulation Number 12 of 2021 Concerning Government Procurement of Goods and Services in the City of Banjarmasin" to perfect this research, as well as increase insight for readers.

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